

Thermal stability of valuable metals in lithium-ion battery cathode materials: Temperature range 100–400 °C

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HIGHLIGHTS

- First step of pyro-hydrometallurgical process: heat treated cathode at 100–400 °C.
- ICP-OES analysis of valuable metals (Li, Ni, Mn, Co).
- Analysis of NMC spinel using XRF, XRD, TGA, SEM/EDS.
- Leaching efficiency of NMC in demineralized water and nitric acid.
- Comparison of yield with other recycling techniques.

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ABSTRACT

Lithium is crucial in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), serving as a main component of the electrolyte and cathode. Elements such as cobalt, nickel, and manganese are also vital for high performance, energy density, and stability. This study aimed to examine the behaviour of end-of-life cathode material (LiNi_{0.6}Mn_{0.2}Co_{0.2}O₂) and its valuable metals after exposure to temperatures between 100 and 400 °C, comparing it with untreated material. The lithium content cannot be reliably determined by conventional analytical methods, so inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) was chosen for this purpose. For ICP-OES measurements, samples were dissolved in different solvents for a specified time, and the concentrations of lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt were measured. From the measured values, their theoretical yields were calculated. Due to the annealing at given temperatures and subsequent dissolution, this step can be considered as the first stage of the pyrometallurgical-hydrometallurgical process used in battery recycling. The study was complemented by further analyses to monitor the effect of annealing temperatures on the properties of the material. Based on the results, it was found that the highest theoretical yield in this temperature range was for material annealed at 400 °C and dissolved in 20 % nitric acid for 4 h.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are considered the most powerful energy storage system for portable electronic devices, wireless devices, hybrid power and electric vehicles (EVs) due to their long life, high energy density, and high voltage [1–3]. For this reason, the LIB industry is one of the fastest growing industries in the world, but the scarce raw

materials such as lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt make it essential to manage these resources effectively. There are various approaches to sustainability in this sector, including battery reuse and recycling. As the amount of spent batteries increases, the waste management will need to be systematically addressed. Recycling is becoming crucial for the renewability of scarce elements [4–6]. An efficient way to dispose of spent LIBs is a key factor for industrial battery manufacturers

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and recyclers. This is important due to the limited resources of strategic metals, the potential negative environmental impact, and the potential to obtain high economic benefits [2,6].

The basic description of a battery cell involves the use of the relationship between the cell potential and the concentrations of individual components. This is described by the Nernst equation (see Equation (1)),

$$\Delta E = \Delta E^0 + \frac{kT}{v_e e} \ln \frac{a_{Ox}}{a_{Red}} \quad (1)$$

where k [JK^{-1}] represents the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature [K], v_e is the number of electrons exchanged, and e stands for elementary charge [C]. The electrode potential ΔE is then described using the natural logarithm of the ratio of chemical activities of the relevant oxidised and reduced components in the system and the standard electrode potential ΔE^0 [7,8].

In essence, LIBs can be defined as energy storage systems that operate through the process of lithium-ion insertion reactions occurring at both the positive and negative electrodes, where lithium ions serve as the charge carriers. This broad categorisation encompasses various cell chemistries that collectively constitute the LIB family. The majority of LIBs typically feature a negative electrode primarily composed of materials such as carbon (e.g., graphite), lithium titanate ($\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$) or innovative materials like metallic lithium and Li(Si) alloys. The choice of electrolyte can vary depending on the electrode materials selected, but typically comprises a blend of lithium salts (e.g. LiPF_6) and an organic solvent (e.g. diethyl carbonate) to facilitate ion transfer. To facilitate the passage of lithium ions between electrodes while preventing the occurrence of internal short circuits, a separating membrane is employed [9–11]. Known examples of materials used as cathodes include lithium cobalt oxide (LiCoO_2), lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO_4) (which can be coated with Ga or SiO_2), lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide ($\text{Li}(\text{Ni}_{1-x-y}\text{Mn}_x\text{Co}_y)\text{O}_2$), lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide ($\text{Li}(\text{Ni}_{1-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Al}_y)\text{O}_2$), and lithium manganese oxide (LiMn_2O_4) [12–15].

The predominant cathode materials used in LIBs for EVs are part of a category of layered mixed transition metal oxide compounds characterised by rhombohedral symmetry (D_{3d}^5 space group). These compounds are represented by the formula $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_{1-x-y}\text{O}_2$ (with $(x + y) \in [0,1]$) and are commonly called NMC [16–18]. The principle of NMC cathode materials lies in the combination of nickel and manganese, each contributing specific attributes. Nickel is known for its high specific energy, but has the drawback of poor stability, while manganese possesses the advantage of forming a spinel structure to reduce internal resistance, though it offers lower specific energy. The specific combination of these metals, nickel and manganese, varies among manufacturers and is closely guarded as a proprietary formula. Researchers are actively exploring nickel-rich electrodes to enhance energy density while reducing the cobalt content to reduce costs. Companies have transitioned from NMC111 to NMC442, NMC622, NMC721 and now anticipate the introduction of NMC811 [9,19,20].

The theoretical capacity of stoichiometric NMC materials is around $275 \text{ mAh} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$, though its accessible capacity depends on the ratio of transition-metal ions within the material. Within the layered transition metal oxide category, cathodes rich in nickel, such as NMC811, exhibit higher capacity and operational voltage, with nickel as the primary active redox species ($\text{Ni}^{2+} \leftrightarrow \text{Ni}^{4+}$). However, nickel-rich compounds often exhibit poor thermal stability. Manganese plays a crucial role in the preservation of battery cycle life and safety, while cobalt enhances electronic conductivity, improving rate capability. Commercially, NMC111 and NMC333 have reached a more mature stage, incorporating the benefits of various transition metals [21]. For nickel-rich NMC materials, the accessible capacity is significantly higher than NMC111 but faces challenges such as cation mixing [22], surface reconstruction to rock salt [23], phase transformation [24], particle cracking [25], transition metal dissolution [26] and parasitic reactions with electrolyte [27].

Cathode scrap stands out as the most precious element for recovery in the context of spent LIBs, given its abundance of valuable metals such as lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt. Consequently, a well-defined framework has been put in place to facilitate its retrieval. Nowadays, the techniques employed to recycle cathode scrap mainly encompass hydrometallurgical methods, pyrometallurgical methods, combined pyrometallurgical-hydrometallurgical methods, and innovative techniques such as molten salt, deep eutectic solvent methods or fluorine-rich hydrogel for extracting Li^+ from Li-containing solutions [1,28–31].

Sieber et al. conducted experiments on identical materials using a wide range of acids, such as HCl and HNO_3 , as well as other chemicals like citric acid and NaOH. The samples were leached at laboratory temperature with constant stirring. A more sophisticated method to achieve higher yields involved the use of a high-pressure microwave digestion system. The solutions containing dissolved valuable metals were analysed using ICP-OES. Our proposed method similarly aims to increase process yield but does so by pre-treating the cathode material with thermal stress. Lower temperatures were selected to avoid unnecessary increases in environmental and economic costs. Yang et al. also employed thermal pre-treatment at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ followed by leaching in H_2O_2 at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a method we sought to avoid due to its energy intensity. Furthermore, Yang et al. did not consider the efficiency of this process for recovering lithium, which we believe is a critical element for the overall efficiency of the process. Our study emphasizes the significance of lithium recovery and strives to present a more sustainable and economically viable approach by optimizing pre-treatment conditions and leaching processes [32,33].

This work focused on the behaviour of the end-of-life cathode material NMC622 from LIB cell when exposed to different temperatures. The key point was to determine the content of valuable metals that are released from the material with increasing temperature. This can then determine the temperature at which the highest yield of valuable metals will be obtained for possible further processing. Therefore, inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) was chosen as the main analysis, which is one of the few methods that can quantitatively determine the lithium content of the material. Other monitored elements were nickel, manganese, and cobalt. A whole set of samples was prepared and annealed for 1 h each at temperatures of $100\text{--}800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, however, due to the number of results obtained, this paper focuses only on temperatures of $100\text{--}400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the results dealing with the behaviour of the material at temperatures of $500\text{--}800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ will be described in following article. For ICP-OES measurements, the material was dissolved in two different solvents, namely nitric acid and demineralized water. Demineralized water was chosen due to its safety, low economic cost, and also because lithium has the potential to be recovered by water. Material that has not been exposed to heat was used as a reference sample. In order to get a comprehensive picture of the material behaviour at different temperatures, other methods were used, namely X-ray diffraction (XRD) and fluorescence (XRF), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDS). Thus, the results described below represent a comprehensive material analysis of the end-of-life NMC622.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Chemicals

Nitric acid (HNO_3) used in this study was of analytical grade and was purchased from Lach-Ner, s.r.o. (Neratovice, Czech Republic). The single element lithium standard (99,99 % Li_2CO_3 in 2 % HNO_3 , ANALYTICA, s.r.o., Czech Republic) and the multi-element standard of 26 elements (in 5 % HNO_3 , ANALYTICA, s.r.o., Czech Republic) were used as calibration standards for ICP-OES measurements.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Disassembly procedure

The LIB module, which is commonly used in battery electric vehicles (BEVs), was selected for material analysis. This module consists of 24 NMC pouch cells, each cell has a voltage of 3.65 V and a capacity of 78 Ah, which create the base for the nominal module voltage of 29.36 V. The module was short-circuited to ensure safe handling prior to disassembly, and was then manually disassembled into its individual parts, i. e. milling off the aluminium casing, removing the polyurethane and polymer materials used as electrical and thermal insulation. The remaining plastic and metal coverings were then removed and the individual cells separated [34].

2.2.2. Sample preparation

The LIB pouch cell was disassembled into individual layers of cathodes, anodes, and separators. The cathode material including the aluminium foil was manually cut into square pieces with a size of 25 × 25 mm. These samples were placed in a porcelain crucible and heat treated in an electric furnace at a temperature of 100, 200, 300 and 400 °C for 60 min with a temperature gradient of 5 °C/min in air atmosphere. The samples were labelled according to the firing temperature (e.g. a sample treated at 100 °C for 1 h is named NMC101, etc.). A reference sample that was not exposed to heat treatment is labelled as NMC0. For ICP-OES analysis, the burnt cathode material was finely cut with scissors into strips with a defined area of 17.5 ± 2.5 mm². The samples were then dissolved in 25 mL of demineralized water or 20 % nitric acid solution, respectively, for 1.5, 2 and 4 h. The suspension was diluted 500 times, filtered, and analysed by ICP-OES.

All samples were analysed using X-ray diffraction and fluorescence. Samples designated as NMC0 through NMC301 were examined as compact materials due to the difficulty in separating them from the aluminium current collector. In contrast, the sample designated as NMC401 was analysed in powdered form. The NMC401 sample was placed in 80 mL of distilled water in a plastic container. A SONOPULS HD 2200.2 ultrasonic homogeniser with an ultrasonic generator GM 2200.2 and an ultrasonic converter UW 2200 (all BANDELIN, Germany) was used for separation. The amplitude was set to 30 %, the sonication time was 2 × 5 min. The distilled water was poured through a sieve to separate the aluminium parts, and the poured distilled water containing NMC particles was evaporated in an evaporating dish in an oven at 95 °C to constant weight. The dried powdered material was ground in an agate pestle and mortar to obtain a fine powder. The NMC0 sample could not be separated, so it was analysed as a compact sample.

2.2.3. X-ray fluorescence analysis

X-ray fluorescence analysis was conducted using an Axios sequential wavelength-dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WD-XRF) spectrometer. The instrument used for the analysis was equipped with an Rh anode end-window X-ray tube of type 4 GN, featuring a 75 µm Be window. Acquisition of peak intensity data was performed using the SuperQ 5.0 software. The measurements were made under vacuum conditions. The generator settings-collimator-crystal-detector combinations were optimised for collecting 11 scans for all 83 measured elements, for many elements are more than one X-ray line available. The collected data were subsequently processed and quantified using Omnia standard analysis software. The measurement time was about 20 min.

2.2.4. Scanning electron microscopy

The scanning electron microscope TESCAN VEGA 3 LMU (SEM) in secondary electron (SE) mode was used to determine the composition of the materials used and measure their particle size (VEGA3 software). All images were taken at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV, with a working distance of 15 mm and a magnification of 2000×. The OXFORD Instruments INCA 350 EDS analyser enables chemical microanalysis of the observed sample, which is then evaluated in the AZtec software version

4.4. The composition was repeatedly measured on an area of 0.005 mm².

2.2.5. X-ray diffraction analysis

X-ray powder diffraction measurements were conducted at room temperature using a PANanalytical X'Pert PRO 0-θ powder diffractometer featuring parafocusing Bragg-Brentano geometry, and CoK_α radiation (λ = 1.79028 Å) at a 35 kV X-ray tube voltage and a current of 40 mA. Data acquisition utilised a high-speed detector X'Celerator. Subsequent data analysis and interpretation were carried out using the software package HighScore Plus 4.0.

2.2.6. Thermal properties

Thermogravimetric measurement was performed on Discovery TGA550 Auto Advanced in air atmosphere (air, technical grade, SIAD s. r.o.) at heating rate 10 °C/min from room temperature to 1000 °C, sample weight approximately 15 mg.

2.2.7. Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES)

The concentrations of elements of Li, Ni, Mn and Co were determined by the inductively coupled plasma emission spectrometer 5900 ICP-OES (Agilent, USA). The plasma was generated from the Ar flow using a water-cooled semiconductor radiofrequency generator with a frequency of 27 Hz and a power of 1.2 kW. The measurements were performed in the so-called synchronous vertical dual view (SVDV) mode, which allows measurements in axial and radial views simultaneously. Quantitative analysis was based on a five-point calibration series for each measured element, ranging from 0.2 to 1.0 mg/L. The results are based on three measurements of each sample.

3. Results

3.1. Composition and structure

Composition and structure were monitored using XRF and XRD on all samples from the thermally untreated sample (NMC0) to the sample annealed to the highest temperature investigated (NMC401). For comparison, SEM/EDS analysis was also conducted on the same set of samples.

The XRF analysis of the chemical composition (see Table 1) of the untreated sample NMC0 identified nickel oxide (56.2 wt%), manganese oxide (13.4 wt%) and cobalt oxide (11.7 wt%) as the major elements. Other minor elements were aluminium, which corresponds to the material from which the current collector is made, phosphorus, and fluorine, which come from other parts of the battery, such as electrolytes or binder used for the cathode material. Another identified minor element was tungsten. It is likely a dopant in the form of, for example, tungsten

Table 1

Chemical composition in wt.% analysed by XRF in the reference material (NMC0) and in the heat-treated materials (NMC101-401).

Analysed composition [wt. %]	Sample				
	NMC0	NMC101	NMC201	NMC301	NMC401
Al ₂ O ₃	0.6 ± 0.0	1.6 ± 0.0	1.0 ± 0.0	0.8 ± 0.0	7.0 ± 0.1
P ₂ O ₅	2.3 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.0	2.3 ± 0.0	1.5 ± 0.0	1.0 ± 0.0
F	15.2 ± 0.6	9.5 ± 0.5	15.7 ± 0.6	8.9 ± 0.5	2.9 ± 0.2
MnO	13.4 ± 0.1	14.3 ± 0.1	13.4 ± 0.1	14.4 ± 0.1	14.4 ± 0.1
Co ₃ O ₄	11.7 ± 0.1	12.5 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.1	12.6 ± 0.1	12.9 ± 0.1
NiO	56.2 ± 0.2	60.0 ± 0.2	55.5 ± 0.2	61.3 ± 0.2	61.3 ± 0.1
WO ₃	0.6 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0

oxide (WO₃), aimed at improving electron conductivity and enhancing the kinetics of redox reactions in cathode materials [30].

Some changes in composition, particularly in the content of minor compounds, occur as a result of heat exposure. Specifically, a decrease in the content of P₂O₅, F, and WO₃ is observed, while the content of Al₂O₃, MnO, Co₃O₄, and NiO increases.

The increase in Al₂O₃ and the decrease in P₂O₅ and F can be attributed to the thermal treatment process of the PVDF-based polymer binder in the battery electrolyte. During heat treatment, fluorine and phosphorus components are prone to evaporate or undergo chemical transformations, leading to a reduction in their presence within the material. Since the composition analysis is always recalculated to 100 %, any decrease in F and P₂O₅ will naturally result in an increase in other components, including Al₂O₃. However, it is also possible that the increased content of Al₂O₃ could be attributed to the precipitation of Al compounds on the NMC particles, as discussed in Ref. [32]. It is conceivable that during the separation process of NMC particles from Al foil in demineralized water, this phenomenon occurred. The increased content of F in the NMC201 sample is consistent with the results of the XRD analysis (Fig. 2d), where the crystalline phase Li₂NiF₄ is observed.

The SEM/EDS results (see Table 2) are consistent with the findings obtained from XRF. They confirm a decrease in the content of minor components of the material, accompanied by an increase in Ni, Mn, and Co element. This indicates that the organic components of the material and compounds from the PVDF binder and electrolyte evaporate with increasing temperature. The EDS analysis results showed a significant decrease in F content, particularly between samples exposed to 300 °C (NMC301) and 400 °C (NMC401). The majority of impurities from other battery components evaporate between these temperatures, as evidenced by the sharp decline in C content.

Fig. 1 presents images obtained using a scanning electron microscope of the cathode material surface. On the left side of each subfigure, the images were captured in secondary electron (SE) mode. On the right side, EDS maps of the elements Ni, Mn, Co, and F are displayed. No significant changes were observed between the samples, except that the EDS maps indicate a decrease in fluorine content with increasing annealing temperature. This suggests a reduction in the polymer binder as the temperature rises.

X-ray diffraction analysis (see Fig. 2) confirmed the presence of the crystalline phase LiNi_{0.6}Mn_{0.2}Co_{0.2}O₂ (ICDD 01-084-9844) in all samples, corresponding to the NMC622 composition. The results indicate that heat treatment of the samples in the selected temperature range of 100–400 °C does not affect the material's structure, except for the sample heated to 200 °C (NMC201). At this temperature, the phase Li₂NiF₄ was identified, suggesting a structural change in the material. This phase likely originates from either the reaction between cathode material and the electrolyte or from the decomposition of PVDF. All identified peaks were properly labelled in the diffractogram. Subsequent chemical analysis, as detailed in Table 1, revealed NiO, MnO, and Co₃O₄ as predominant oxides, with NMC0 exhibiting a relatively elevated fluorine content compared to the NMC401 specimen. This disparity

Table 2

The chemical composition of the cathode material at different thermal exposures performed by EDS, given in wt.%.

Element	Sample				
	NMC0	NMC101	NMC201	NMC301	NMC401
Al	0.5 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.1
F	19.9 ± 0.1	20.6 ± 0.5	20.7 ± 0.2	20.8 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 0.3
Ni	30.2 ± 0.1	26.9 ± 1.1	29.6 ± 0.2	32.0 ± 0.2	47.9 ± 1.7
Mn	9.4 ± 0.1	9.1 ± 0.4	9.2 ± 0.1	9.9 ± 0.1	14.2 ± 0.8
Co	7.2 ± 0.1	6.8 ± 0.6	7.0 ± 0.1	7.7 ± 0.1	12.3 ± 1.1
W	1.2 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.2
P	0.6 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.1	0.60 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0	0.8 ± 0.1
C	9.0 ± 0.2	9.0 ± 1.4	9.3 ± 0.2	8.7 ± 0.2	3.7 ± 0.4
O	22.1 ± 0.1	23.8 ± 0.6	22.0 ± 0.1	18.8 ± 0.1	16.9 ± 0.6

aligns with the characteristics of the binder used, which exhibits a higher melting point. Other elements or oxides were present only in marginal proportions.

3.2. Thermal analysis

Thermogravimetric measurement of sample NMC0 in air atmosphere (Fig. 3) showed a small weight loss up to 230 °C which is attributed to electrolyte loss. The decomposition between 230 and 630 °C took place in two main steps with peaks at 270 and 540 °C; the loss in this interval is mainly attributed to the decomposition of the present polymers. Significant thermooxidation, followed by mass loss, was observed at temperatures above 750 °C. Most of the observed changes occur outside our studied temperature range (above 400 °C).

3.3. Concentrations of Li, Ni, Mn, and Co

The results of the ICP-OES analysis showed that the measured concentration depends on the dissolution time, the type of solvent, and the temperature to which the initial material was exposed. In a 20 % HNO₃ solution (see Fig. 4), the measured concentrations were several times higher than in demineralized water. In terms of the dependence of the measured concentration on the dissolution time, the highest values were measured after 4 h. For the NMC101 and NMC301 samples, a significant decrease in concentration was observed after 2 h of dissolution, indicating that precipitation of the determined ions occurred in the solution.

The temperature to which the initial material was exposed before dissolution also plays an important role, as can be seen from the graphs, the concentrations of Ni, Mn, and Co are significantly higher in the case of material exposed to temperatures of 300 and 400 °C, respectively. This phenomenon is likely associated with the melting temperature of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), the binder used in the manufacture of these batteries, which could affect the thermal stability and performance of the battery cells. Nickel was the most leached element from the NMC material, followed by manganese, cobalt, and the lowest values were measured for lithium. The mean relative standard deviations were 0.24 % for lithium, 0.31 % for nickel, 0.42 % for manganese and 0.39 % for cobalt.

Zhang et al. described how PVDF affects the dissolution of the cathode material after thermal treatment due to its semicrystalline nature that allows the electrolyte to contact the active material directly, increasing dissolution and solubility in solutions. Additionally, the PVDF polymer primarily relies on weaker van der Waals forces, leading to significant thermal expansion. This large volume expansion can increase the internal pressure of the battery, further exposing the active material to the electrolyte, contributing to higher solubility, performance deterioration, and safety issues [35].

Demineralized water was chosen as the second type of solvent because it is much safer to use than acids. After dissolution in demineralized water, only lithium concentrations were measured (see Fig. 5), which were almost constant after 2 h of dissolution. For the other elements, it would be appropriate to choose a different procedure or solvent type for quantitative analysis due to the values that were below the detection limit of the instrument. The mean relative standard deviation was 0.31 %.

3.4. Theoretical valuable metal yield

To determine the yield, the maximal theoretical amount was computed utilising the technical datasheet specifications. The cathode material composes 42.5 % of a cell. Therefore from

$$m_{\text{cathode}} = m_{\text{pack}} \cdot \frac{p}{100} \quad (2)$$

where p is a portion of the active cathode material, and the cathode mass of a cell is

Fig. 1. Scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive spectroscopy of the cathode material surface for samples (a) NMC0, (b) NMC101, (c) NMC201, (d) NMC301 and (e) NMC401.

$$M_{cathode} = 0.458 \text{ kg} \quad (3)$$

The mole and mass quantities of individual elements of $\text{Li}_{1.0}\text{Ni}_{0.6}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ were calculated based on formula

$$n_A = u_A \cdot \frac{m_{cathode}}{M_{cathode}} \quad (4)$$

where n_A is the number of moles of the respective element, u_A is the stoichiometric coefficient [4]. From the mass concentration measured by ICP-OES, the mass of dissolved ions was calculated for the highest measured concentrations, in this case for samples dissolved for 4 h (see Table 3a). From this mass, the theoretical yield of valuable metals obtained by dissolution in 20 % nitric acid solution and demineralized water, respectively, was calculated. The results shown (see Table 3b) are for the NMC401 sample after 4 h of dissolution.

The masses of dissolved valuable metals increase with increasing annealing temperature of the sample. The highest results are obtained for the sample annealed at 400 °C. The dissolution in nitric acid gave a lithium yield almost five times higher than that obtained in demineralized water.

The efficiency of this method was compared with the available results of the hydrometallurgical method. The highest recovery (91 %) was found for nickel; the recovery of the other elements studied ranged from

60 to 70 % using acid. In demineralized water, the highest lithium recovery was 14 %.

4. Discussion

The cathode sample was subjected to thermal exposure and subsequently dissolved in appropriate solvents to simulate the initial stages of the pyrometallurgical-hydrometallurgical process. Annealing temperatures of 100, 200, 300 and 400 °C were applied for 1 h each, and dissolution was carried out for 1.5, 2 and 4 h. Changes after both thermal treatment and dissolution in the specified solvents were closely monitored.

Chemical composition analysis revealed a reduction in the fluorine and phosphorus content with an increase in the temperature to which the material was exposed. This suggests that, as the temperature rises, the binder undergoes decomposition and any residual electrolyte adhering to the cathode samples is burnt off. The XRD results indicate that the material composition remains NMC622 after exposure to heat.

Examination of the samples using an SEM/EDS instrument confirmed the loss of binder with increasing temperature, as depicted in the attached photographs. Furthermore, consistent trends in chemical composition were observed, as observed in the X-ray fluorescence

Fig. 1. (continued).

results - specifically, a decrease in the content of fluorine and phosphorus in the case of sample NMC401.

The TGA results confirmed that the binder decomposition occurs within the temperature range of 230–630 °C. This discovery implies that the material can undergo heat treatment at lower temperatures, such as 400 °C, allowing reutilization of the active material. At this temperature,

most of the binder has already undergone decomposition, while the structure of the NMC remains intact. This not only minimises recycling expenses, but also ensures the feasibility of material reuse.

Measurements from ICP-OES indicated that the concentration of lithium, nickel, manganese, and cobalt is dependent on the dissolution time and, notably, on the temperature to which the initial material was

Fig. 2. XRD analysis of NMC0-NMC401.

exposed. As the temperature increased, the concentration of all elements also increased, with the highest concentration observed in the case of sample NMC401. This further supports the notion that annealing decomposed the binder, leading to the release of a higher quantity of ions into the solution from the sample subjected to the highest temperature. From the measured concentrations, the masses of dissolved ions were calculated and from these the efficiency of the process was calculated and compared to the efficiency of metal recovery from spent NMC using the hydrometallurgical method, which is the most similar in principle to our method due to the low temperatures used in our study. The theoretical efficiency of our method was similar in the case of nickel recovery (we achieved 91 %), while it was lower for the other elements investigated. This is probably due to the use of a different solvent. In the compared study, sulfuric acid was used in combination with hydrogen peroxide [36]; in this work, nitric acid was used as the solvent. Although the lithium yield obtained by dissolving the material in demineralized

water was fourteen times higher than in the other reported study [32], dissolution in acid gave much higher results. The higher yield obtained in our study is probably due to the longer dissolution time; on the other hand, most of the lithium is released into solution at the beginning of the process, so the heat treatment of the sample, which was carried out in this paper, will have a great influence here. Due to the highest yields at the highest temperature investigated, this work will be followed by the investigation of material fired at higher temperatures, and therefore there is the potential for further release of the binder at higher temperatures, and therefore higher yields.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the analyses, the cathode material retains its structure even when exposed to temperatures of 100–400 °C. XRD confirmed the structure of NMC622 even after annealing the material at

Fig. 3. TGA curve of the sample NMC0.

the studied temperatures (100–400 °C). However, decomposition of the binder or leaching of electrolyte residues occurs in this temperature range, and therefore changes in composition were observed (XRF, EDS). The effect of annealing temperature is most clearly observed in the graphs showing the dependence of concentration on dissolution time, with sample NMC401 reaching the highest measured concentrations, and always after 4 h of dissolution. From these concentrations, the theoretical valuable metal yield was calculated, which is highest at the highest temperature investigated. From this it can be said that annealing at 400 °C for 1 h followed by dissolution in 20 % nitric acid for 4 h leads to the highest yield. The efficiency of the process was 91 % for nickel, while for the other metals studied it was in the range of 60–70 %, which is a lower yield compared to other methods; however, nitric acid, as the solvent used is cheaper compared to other solvents used. At the same

time, e.g., the pyrometallurgical method involves smelting of the material at very high temperatures (around 1500 °C), so our method could significantly reduce both the economic and environmental associated with the pre-treatment of the material. A comprehensive evaluation that compares our method with conventional recycling pre-treatment techniques and an analysis of the potential economic benefits is intended for future research. By dissolving in demineralized water, an efficiency of around 14 % was achieved, which is much higher than in another study where around 1 % was achieved. Therefore, dissolution in acid is more efficient in terms of yield; on the other hand, dissolution in water is a highly safe and more environmentally friendly. Since the highest yields of valuable metals were found at the highest observed annealing temperature, as well as binder decomposition, and it is therefore possible that complete binder decomposition occurs at higher temperatures, a follow-up experiment will be developed to investigate the behaviour of the same material at higher temperatures, specifically in the 500–800 °C range.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Nikola Klusoňová: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Eliška Sedláčková:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jan Kočí:** Data curation, Conceptualization, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dominik Pilnaj:** Methodology, Data curation. **Karolína Pánová:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jonáš Uříčár:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Václav Procházka:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Kristýna Jílková:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Anna Pražanová:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Conceptualization. **Martin**

(a) Lithium

(b) Nickel

(c) Manganese

(d) Cobalt

Fig. 4. Concentration of (a) lithium; (b) nickel; (c) manganese and (d) cobalt dissolved in 20 % HNO₃.

Fig. 5. Concentration of lithium dissolved in demineralized water.

Table 3

(a) Mass [16] of valuable metals from a sample (100 mg) determined from the measured concentration after 4 h of dissolution; (b) Comparison of the efficiency [%] of the hydrometallurgical method and with the results of our work.

(a)					
	Our study				
	NMC0	NMC101	NMC201	NMC301	NMC401
Lithium in HNO ₃	3.2	3.7	3.8	4.5	4.7
Lithium in demin. water	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.7	1.0
Nickel in HNO ₃	13.2	14.7	16.6	23.4	28.3
Manganese in HNO ₃	3.6	4.1	4.5	6.6	8.1
Cobalt in HNO ₃	3.0	3.3	3.8	5.3	6.9
(b)					
Methods	Leaching agent	Leaching condition	Efficiency [%]	Ref.	
Hydrometallurgy	H ₂ SO ₄ + H ₂ O ₂	40 °C, 1 h	Li, Ni, Mn, Co = 99.7	[36]	
	deionised water	room temperature 30–60 min	Li = 1.0	[32]	
Our study	HNO ₃	pre-treated at 400 °C room temperature 4 h	Li = 69.9, Ni = 91.0, Mn = 63.6, Co = 60.4	–	
	demineralized water	pre-treated at 400 °C room temperature 4 h	Li = 14.4	–	

Havlík Míka: Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Nikola Klusonova reports financial support was provided by University of Chemistry and Technology Prague. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

I have shared the link to my data at the Attach File step.

Dataset of "Thermal Stability of Valuable Metals in Lithium-Ion Battery Cathode Materials: Temperature Range 100–400 °C" (Original data) (Zenodo)

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